

Advancements in rangeland livestock management: new technologies meet the old frontier of extensive grazing systems

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Abstract

Over the last 20 years, global positioning system (GPS) collars have revolutionized livestock grazing behavior research. Practices designed to improve livestock grazing distribution can now be accurately and cost effectively monitored with GPS tracking. For example, cattle use of feed supplement placed in areas far from water and on steep slopes can be measured with GPS tracking and corresponding impacts on distribution patterns estimated. Ongoing research has identified genetic markers that are associated with cattle spatial movement patterns. If the results can be validated, genetic selection for grazing distribution may become feasible. Tracking collars have become easier to develop and construct, making them significantly less expensive, which will likely increase their use in livestock grazing management research. Some research questions can be designed so that dependent variables are measured by spatial movements of livestock, and in such cases, GPS tracking is a practical tool for conducting studies on extensive and rugged rangeland pastures. Similarly, accelerometers are changing our ability to monitor livestock behaviour. Today, accelerometers are sensitive and can record movements at fine temporal scales for periods of weeks to months. The combination of GPS tracking and accelerometers appear to be useful tools for identifying changes in livestock behavior that are associated with livestock diseases and other welfare concerns. Recent technological advancements may make real time or near-real time tracking on rangelands feasible. This would allow development of applications that could remotely monitor livestock well-being on extensive rangeland and notify ranchers when animals require treatment or other management.

Background

Livestock management on rangelands present different challenges than intensive livestock systems (Bailey, 2016). On rangelands, animals graze extensive and often rugged pastures. It is often a challenge to find all the livestock in a paddock, and normal management practices of checking water availability and animal well-being require additional labor compared to intensive systems. Large pasture size and rugged terrain also make livestock research more difficult. Prior to GPS technologies, observers followed cattle and sheep on horseback or on foot and periodically estimated their position and recorded it. This was especially difficult at night. The length of tracking was often only 1 or 2 days at a time, and location accuracy and the impact of the observer on the livestock were also issues. About 20 years ago, GPS collars became commercially available and began to be used in livestock grazing research (Turner et al., 2000; Swain et al., 2011). The ability to accurately track livestock on a 24 hour basis for weeks and months revolutionized livestock behavior and grazing management research and dramatically increased the number of studies evaluating distribution practices and livestock spatial movement patterns. The only limitation to this technology was the cost of commercial GPS collars, which is currently \$1500 to \$2000 per collar. Scientists often could not afford to track as many individual animals as they desired. Clark et al. (2006) developed a GPS collar that was less expensive (< \$1000 USD) than commercial collars. Recently, low-cost GPS data loggers have been used to build tracking that cost between \$150 to \$300 (Allan et al., 2013; Knight, 2016). Studies using livestock tracking have increased as the cost of GPS collars have decreased.

Accelerometers can be used to monitor activity. In the past, vibracorders were used to determine cattle activity patterns on pasture. These devices could record the up and down movements of an animals head for several days, which provided relatively good estimates of grazing and resting times (Stobbs, 1970). Commercially available tracking collars often included accelerometers along with the

GPS receiver. The accelerometer recorded animal head movements, and researchers combined this motion sensor data with velocity between recorded locations to classify livestock behaviors, such as grazing, traveling and resting (Ungar et al., 2005; Augustine and Derner, 2013). In the last few years, 3-axis accelerometers have become commercially available and can record movement at very fine temporal scales (e.g., 25 Hz). This fine scale monitoring may allow scientists to detect subtle changes in animal behavior (Barwick, 2017).

Currently, animal motion and location data are usually stored on the sensor device (collar or eartag) and cannot be accessed until the device is removed from the animal. However, technologies continue to evolve and real time or near real time monitoring of location and animal motion data may be commercially available in the foreseeable future. It is likely that these new technologies will expand the use of GPS tracking and motion sensors in rangeland livestock management. The objectives of this paper are to describe how GPS tracking and accelerometer have advanced our ability to manage livestock on extensive and rugged rangelands and to discuss how these technologies may be used in the future.

Management of Grazing Distribution

Livestock distribution is a critical trait and one of the principles of grazing management (Vallentine, 2001). Most of the concerns associated with livestock grazing in the western United States are associated with uneven grazing distribution (Bailey, 2005). Almost all of the proposed tools to improve livestock grazing distribution were described over 60 years ago by Williams (1954), however our ability to test and refine these techniques were limited because of the difficulties and labor required to visually observe livestock grazing patterns. The advent of GPS tracking in the late 1990's allowed researchers to accurately monitor livestock grazing patterns for weeks to months and validate the effectiveness of techniques designed to improve distribution. For example, Ares (1953) and Martin and Ward (1973) used supplements to increase cattle use of areas away from water, but they were not able to measure how the supplements affected animal behaviour. They relied on sampling forage utilization to evaluate the effectiveness of the distribution practice. Later, a series of studies showed that strategic placement of low-moisture blocks changed increased cattle use of areas within 600 m of placement sites and increased loafing near the supplement as well (Bailey et al., 2001; Bailey and Jensen, 2008; Bailey et al., 2008a).

Herding cattle was suggested as a tool to improve grazing distribution in the 1950's (Williams, 1954; Skovlin, 1957), but there were no quantitative studies documenting the effectiveness of this practice for over 50 years. Anecdotal observations suggested that herding reduced cattle use of riparian areas (Butler, 2000), but Bailey et al. (2008b) demonstrated with GPS tracking that low-stress herding changed cattle behavior, decreased use near riparian areas and increased upland grazing. The combination of low-stress herding and strategic supplement placement has been used successfully to target cattle grazing in Arizona (Bruegger et al., 2016) and in New Mexico (Stephenson et al., 2016). In addition to increasing uniformity of forage use, targeted cattle grazing could be used to reduce fine fuel levels in designated areas and potentially reduce the risk and/or severity of wild fires.

A combination of technologies may allow rangeland livestock producers to select cattle for improved grazing distribution. As discussed earlier, GPS tracking provides data that can be used to develop grazing distribution traits. Geographical information system (GIS) software readily calculates the average slope and elevation use of tracked cows from digital elevation maps. It also can be used to develop metrics based on the distance cattle travel from water. These distribution metrics can be considered as "hard to measure traits" because of the cost of GPS tracking collars and complexity cattle movement patterns on rangelands. The bovine high density single nucleotide polymorphism (HDSNP) chip and other genomic technologies provide a new approach to examine the genotypic and phenotypic relationship of complex traits like grazing distribution. Eggen (2012) suggests genomic selection is a promising approach to improve complex traits that are difficult to measure. Using the HDSNP, Bailey et al. (2015) found that genetic markers on chromosomes 4, 8, 17 and 29 were related to indices of terrain use. A single marker or single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) explained up to 24% of the variation a terrain index, while a combination of five SNP explained up to 36% of the variation. Not only does this research demonstrate that terrain use is heritable, but it shows the potential to use genomic selection to improve cattle grazing distribution. A DNA test costing roughly \$30 USD could be used to rank bulls in their ability to sire daughters that are more willing to travel away from water and use rugged terrain. The reduction in cost of GPS collars will allow more cattle to be tracked and enhance this research.

Virtual fencing is another technology that has great promise for managing cattle grazing distribution (Anderson, 2007). In most proposed applications, a GPS receiver tracks the animal's location and audio stimuli and if needed electrical stimuli are used to encourage cattle to avoid certain areas and graze in designated areas. Several proof of concept studies demonstrate the technique can be effective in manipulating where cattle graze (Bishop-Hurley et al., 2007; Anderson et al., 2014). Research on virtual fencing has been conducted from the 1990 (Quigley et al., 1990) to present (Umstatter et al., 2015), but commercial applications of this technology have not been developed. Some problems that have limited development of virtual fencing are the result of our understanding of cattle behavioral responses to the adverse stimuli (Markus et al., 2014), but the cost, weight and reliability of the system are limiting factors (Anderson et al., 2014). Commercial development of virtual fencing continues to be pursued (e.g., Argensens eShepard, <http://agersens.com/eshepherd/>).

Potential of Real-Time Tracking and Motion Sensing

The most obvious benefit of real-time tracking is the ability to readily find your livestock in extensive and rugged rangeland pastures. A majority of the time required to gather cattle and move them to corrals for husbandry practices, such as branding or weaning, is to simply find the animals. The time required for locating animals is one of the major reasons that helicopters are used to herd cattle in Australia. Real-time tracking could also be used to reduce the incidence of stock-theft. Movement patterns associated with being gathered and moved could be used to detect unauthorized herding and potential stock theft. A monitoring system could alert managers before the animals left the property.

Monitoring livestock welfare is different on rangelands than in intensive systems (Bailey, 2016). Animals are often not seen by managers and/or staff for days or even weeks. Correspondingly, animals that become ill may often be not treated as quickly as those raised in intensive systems. If real time tracking and animal sensing can be used to detect disease and other welfare concerns remotely, this technology could be used to inform management that treatment or other management actions are needed. Although much more research is needed, there are some studies that demonstrate the potential for GPS tracking to detect animal well-being concerns. Dobos et al. (2014) were able to detect when ewes lambed using GPS tracking. Preliminary analyses of a study conducted by the authors and David Scobie and colleagues at AgResearch in New Zealand show that perennial grass staggers can potentially be detected remotely. Sheep grazing in a perennial ryegrass pasture (4350 ± 63 m/day) move slower ($P=0.04$) than sheep in a control pasture (4727 ± 56 m/day). Sheep were also monitored with accelerometers and analyses are pending.

In the near future, commercially available technologies may be able provide accelerometer data to livestock producers on a real time or near real time basis. Recent research demonstrate how accelerometers can be used to detect livestock diseases and welfare concerns. Using a 3-axis accelerometer, Barwick (2017) was able to readily detect lameness in sheep. Analyses being conducted by the authors show that accelerometers may also useful for detecting diseases. As part of a separate study, two of eight heifers being monitored with accelerometers became ill with bovine ephemeral sickness (3-day sickness). Along with high fever, cattle with 3-day sickness dramatically reduce feed intake, become sore, and are depressed. The ill heifers were first observed about noon when they were usually checked. Activity during the early morning, a normal grazing period, clearly dropped on the day the sickness first appeared (Figure 1). This dramatic change in activity as shown by the accelerometer was recorded several hours before they were visually checked. Additional research and analyses are needed to determine if accelerometers can detect the onset of disease before clinical signs can be observed.

Conclusions

The advent GPS tracking has greatly enhanced research and development of tools designed to improve distribution and uniformity of grazing by livestock by allowing them to quantitatively measure changes in animal movements. Genomic technologies combined with GPS tracking and GIS allows researchers the ability to conduct genotype to phenotype association studies of grazing distribution traits and potentially use genomic selection to improve cattle use of steep slopes and areas far from water.

Figure 1. Activity of a heifer at 0700, normal grazing period, the day before being visually detected as ill (day -1) and several hours before being observed with 3-day sickness (day 0). An accelerometer placed on a collar monitored motion in three axes, which was converted to movement intensity (Zhang and Sawchuk, 2011)

Development of real time and near real time monitoring of GPS tracking and motion sensing may allow producers to remotely monitor livestock well-being on extensive rangeland pastures in the near future. Ongoing research suggests that GPS tracking and accelerometer motion sensing can identify livestock diseases and other welfare concerns. Preliminary results are promising, but much more research is needed to determine if GPS tracking and motion sensing can remotely detect disease and welfare concerns remotely and potentially before clinical signs can be observed.

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